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A discrete epigenetic module is a central feature that distinguishes triple negative breast cancer in black women.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Comparing total transcription in the tumors of white women and black women with triple negative cancer revealed differential expression of *SPDYE6* in black women with TNBC. Studying transcriptional patterns across tissues revealed *SPDYE6* is co-regulated with an epigenetic module consisting of MLL2/MLL4, KDM2B, MAZ, ARID1A and MED12.

1 **Results**

2 We studied the TNBC gene expression program by measuring total transcription in tumors from humans
 3 with triple negative breast cancer.

4 **Figure 1:** SPDYE6 is among the greatest transcriptional differences when comparing the tumors of black
 5 women and white women with TNBC.

6 GSE142731

n=16 primary tumors; TNBC (women of white race)

n=19 primary tumors; TNBC (women of black race)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
729597	1.30E-04	0.168	-3.82587	-0.6417802	229.21	SPDYE6	125/19253	99.4

9 GSE241876

n=10 primary tumors; TNBC (women of white race)

n=13 primary tumors; TNBC (women of black race)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
729597	3.89E-02	0.593	-2.06505823	-1.2241001	131.49	SPDYE6	3834/24560	84.4

13 **Figure 2:** SPDYE6 is transcriptionally co-regulated with MLL4 and MLL2.

24 Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	P-Value	Description
SPDYE6	729597	-3.2000	0.0000	speedy homolog E6 (Xenopus laevis)

26 Coexpressed genes:

Query	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	% Co-reg
	MLL4	9757	3.2000	0.0001	1/17783	99.99
	MLL2	8085	3.2000	0.0008	13/17783	99.9

Figure 3: MLL4 and MLL2 identify a module containing ARID1A, MED12, KDM2B, and MAZ .

Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	P-Value	Description
MLL4	9757	-0.2710 0.2292		myeloid/lymphoid or mixed-lineage leukemia 4
MLL2	8085	-0.2328 0.1853		myeloid/lymphoid or mixed-lineage leukemia 2

Query	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	% Co-reg
	ARID1A	8289	2.0443	0.0000	1/17783	99.99
	MED12	9968	1.8188	0.0003	9/17783	99.9
	MAZ	4150	0.9675	0.0522	479/17783	97.3
	KDM2B	84678	0.7377	0.0439	991/17783	94.4

Figure 4: MED12, KDM2B, and MAZ are also identified as genetic background-based disease modifiers in TNBC.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4150	6.06E-04	0.23	-3.42881	-0.7902809	572.34	MAZ	304/19253	98.4
9968	4.58E-03	0.174	-2.835091	-0.4941627	387.96	MED12	936/19253	95.1
57492	3.73E-02	0.173	-2.08283	-0.3597705	661.38	ARID1B	2832/19253	85.3

1 Figure 5: ARID1A, MED12, MAZ, and KDM2B can be retrieved as co-regulated genes using SPDYE6 as
2 query.

3 Query Gene Entrez ID Coexpression Score P-Value Description
SPDYE6 729597 -3.2000 0.0000

4 Coexpressed genes:

Query	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	% Co-reg
	ARID1A	8289	3.0000	0.0086	100/21469	99.5
	MAZ	4150	2.9600	0.0131	112/21469	99.5
	MED12	9968	2.5900	0.0316	262/21469	98.8
	KDM2B	84678	2.5900	0.0083	263/21469	98.8

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Methods

We used the aforementioned RNA sequencing datasets, R-based computational tools for data analysis and SEEK (Princeton) for translational co-regulation study.